

Principals' Leadership Styles, Decision-Making Skills, Communication Forms and Public Senior Secondary Schools Principals' Administrative Effectiveness in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria, seem to have been chastised for their ineffectiveness, as indicated by low teacher engagement, poor record-keeping and low student academic attainment. This study looked into the impact of these characteristics on the administrative performance of public senior high school principals in Oyo State. The study employed a survey research approach, and the population included all 14,402 teachers and 629 principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select 4,204 teachers and all principals in the sampled schools. Teachers Questionnaire (TEQ) ($\alpha = 0.951$) and Principal Interview (PI) were used for data collection. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to answer research questions and test hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The results showed a significant combined influence of leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication forms on the administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State ($F(3,3917) = (21723.35)$; $(Adj. R^2 = 0.923, p < 0.05)$). There was a significant relative influence of these factors on the administrative effectiveness of principals. There were significant differences in communication forms ($t = 2.318, p < 0.05$), decision-making skills ($t = 5.048, p < 0.05$), and administrative effectiveness ($t = 5.435, p < 0.05$) between male and female principals in secondary schools, Oyo State. Public secondary school principals in Oyo State should focus on developing effective leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication forms to enhance their administrative effectiveness.

Keywords: Principal Leadership Styles, Decision-making skills, Communication Forms,

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

Administrative Effectiveness

Introduction

The effectiveness of a leader within an organization can be measured by their success. This success is an indication of their ability to utilise the available resources, both material and human, in order to achieve the goals of the organisation (Pandey 2017). Administrative effectiveness follows certain principles and is not solely about achieving results; it also involves efficiency, which means accomplishing goals while minimising costs (Akinfolarin, 2017). The concept of administrative effectiveness can be understood in terms of the outcomes produced by the leader. In the context of schools, the principal plays a crucial role in administration and is responsible for overseeing instruction and carrying out administrative functions that contribute to administrative effectiveness (Onyali & Akinfolarin, 2017). Effective planning, coordination, supervision, organisation, and direction are necessary to achieve administrative effectiveness. Therefore, this study will specifically focus on planning, coordinating, and supervising.

Planning is a dynamic process that determines the course of future events. It is characterised by flexibility and involves forward-thinking, often requiring scenario planning. According to Pandey (2017), planning encompasses various managerial processes such as perception, analysis, conceptual thinking, communication, decision-making, and taking action. Also, the ability of principals to coordinate effectively stems from their role in management. Principals bear a significant and serious responsibility for internally coordinating and managing schools. Furthermore, the concept of supervision, like other ideas within the arts and humanities, is subject to varying definitions by different scholars and professionals. Supervision involves a process wherein a more experienced professional engages in a friendly and cooperative manner with a less experienced professional, aiming to enhance the successful accomplishment of a given task.

There are several challenges that hinder the effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Nigeria. These challenges encompass insufficient funding, inadequate infrastructure, a deficient capacity-building programme, a shortage of qualified teachers, inadequate ICT

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

infrastructure, a lack of instructional resources, inadequate supervision and security concerns, weak leadership, ineffective decision-making skills, and inadequate communication methods, among others. These issues may impact the performance of both students and teachers in the classroom. The subsequent paragraphs will delve into the leadership style, decision-making skills, and communication forms relevant to this study.

Leadership holds great importance in all human organisations and is widely recognised as a crucial element for effective administrative processes. Within the educational context, the school principal serves as the primary leader and bears responsibility for managing and organising the school. In the educational system, the principal's knowledge, leadership style, experience, expertise, capability, and problem-solving abilities are vital factors in achieving desired outcomes. It is important to note that the concept of leadership style can vary from person to person and situation to situation. Therefore, this study will examine the following leadership styles: autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital.

Autocratic leadership style do not involve others in the decision-making process and instead exert control with a strict approach (Siddique & Siddique, 2019; Akparep, Jengre, & Mogre, 2019; Lundmark, Richter, & Tafvelin, 2022). All decisions are made without seeking the input or approval of the staff. Typically, these leaders do not provide explanations for their actions and remain uncompromising in their stance (Du, Li, & Luo, 2020; Dai & Spires, 2018). According to Hensellek (2020), the democratic leadership style involves the active participation of all group members in the decision-making process. Kokot, Kokotec, and Calopa (2021) state that a democratic leader seeks input from the team while making decisions and addressing issues while maintaining ultimate control over the final solution. Laissez-faire signifies a "hands-off, let things ride" approach to influencing people in the workplace, as noted by Wasono and Furinto (2018). It is defined as the absence of leadership and the avoidance of intervention in a study. Laissez-faire leaders, according to Westerman, Bonnet, and McAfee (2014), often behave as if they have relinquished their responsibilities and obligations. Also, an effective digital leader possesses a clear understanding of the organisatioanal's goals and comprehends how their responsibilities contribute to the achievement of those goals. According to Sheninger (2014), an

organisation that effectively leverages its digital assets to establish and sustain a competitive advantage can be regarded as a digital leader at the organisational level.

Decision-making can be defined as the process of choosing one option from several alternatives with the aim of achieving a desired outcome. The main purpose of decision-making is to guide human behaviour and dedication towards a future objective (Temelkova, 2018). If there are no other options available or no need to make a choice, decision-making becomes unnecessary. Decision-making encompasses a range of skills, including time management, emotional intelligence, problem-solving ability, confidence, adaptability, creative thinking, risk assessment, weighing pros and cons, analytical and critical thinking, as well as information gathering and analysis, among others. However, this study will specifically focus on problem-solving, time management, and emotional intelligence.

Making decisions and fixing problems go hand in hand. Decision-making has its roots in economics and research into business operations, while problem solving was initially characterised by psychologists in a study of how people think (AchmetliSchukajlow & Rakoczy, 2019). Time management skills are essential abilities that individuals must regularly employ. They involve effectively and efficiently utilising time (Harris & Jones, 2020). These skills enable individuals to allocate adequate time for all necessary tasks and activities. According to Harris and Jones (2020), "emotional intelligence" refers to an individual's ability to recognise and identify emotions, generate and regulate emotions, and consequently achieve a state of reflection. Emotional intelligence encompasses a range of non-cognitive abilities, competencies, and skills that enable individuals to effectively handle and navigate environmental demands and pressures.

Effective communication plays a crucial role in efficient management. Communication is essential for every organisation and serves as a managerial tool that executives utilise to influence operations through interpersonal relationships. An administrator's ability to communicate effectively with their team, peers, and stakeholders can significantly impact the success or failure of an organisation. Communication encompasses diverse methods through which individuals and groups convey information, ideas, and opinions; these are referred to as

communication forms. Communication can be categorised in various ways, such as verbal/oral, written, and non-verbal.

Oral communication encompasses the exchange of information using spoken language and is commonly employed in direct conversations, telephone discussions, presentations, speeches, and discussions. It serves as a means of immediate and interactive interaction, facilitating temporary communication requirements. Non-verbal communication, as defined by Bonaccio, O'Reilly, O'Sullivan, and Chiochio (2016), refers to the exchange and interpretation of information using methods other than language. Hall, Horgan, and Murphy (2019) propose that non-verbal communication occurs more frequently than verbal communication, accounting for more than half of human communication. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate principals' leadership styles, decision-making skills and communication forms as determinants of public senior secondary schools administrative effectiveness in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, there seems to have been widespread dissatisfaction with the administrative effectiveness of many public secondary school principals in Nigeria, particularly in Oyo State. Evidence of this ineffectiveness includes low levels of teacher engagement, teachers' lack of responsiveness to the teaching profession, disciplinary issues among students and staff, inadequate record keeping, improper coordination of admission and examination procedures, low academic achievement and performance among students, as well as low levels of teacher dedication and job satisfaction. These irregularities may be attributed to the ineffective administration of public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria. It is likely that schools led by incompetent principals who lack digital knowledge and appropriate leadership styles and communication forms for administrative effectiveness will struggle to achieve educational goals. Studies have identified various factors that contribute to the problems faced by principals in effectively administering secondary schools, including poor working environments, a lack of digitalization among principals, inadequate decision-making skills, ineffective communication forms, unfavourable government policies, a lack of teacher cooperation,

insufficient staff, and inadequate funding (Friedländer, Röber, & Schaefer, 2021). However, there seems to be a gap in research regarding the impact of digital leadership styles and communication forms on the administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria. Therefore, this study aims to investigate on leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication forms as determinants of administrative effectiveness of principals in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the influence of principal leadership styles, decision-making skills and communication forms on public senior secondary school administrative effectiveness in Oyo State. The objectives are to:

- i. identify the level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) of public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria.
- ii. identify the prevalent leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital leadership) that is being adopted by public secondary school administrators in Oyo State, Nigeria.
- iii. identify the prominent decision-making skills (problem-solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) that is being used among principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria .
- iv. determine the prominent communication forms (oral and non-oral) that is being used by secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria.
- v. examine the combined influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), communication forms (oral and non-oral), and decision-making skills (problem solving, time management, and emotional intelligence) on administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.
- vi. examine the relative influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), communication forms (oral and non-oral), and decision-making skills (problem-solving, time management, and emotional intelligence) on administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, the following research questions are posed to be answered.

1. What is the level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state, Nigeria?
2. What is the most prevalent leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital) among public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of decision-making skills (problem-solving, time management, and emotional intelligence) among principals in public secondary schools in Oyo state, Nigeria?
4. What is the prominent communication forms (oral and non-oral) used by public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There will be no significant combined influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo state, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There will be no significant relative influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in public secondary schools in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a survey-type descriptive research design, which was deemed appropriate because the variables under investigation were already established and outside the researcher's control. This design allowed for an accurate depiction of the decision-making abilities and administrative effectiveness of principals.

Selection of participants

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

To ensure a representative sample of the study's population, a multistage sampling procedure was employed using both stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Initially, the state of Oyo was divided into three strata using the existing senatorial districts: Oyo Central, North, and South. Next, local governments with the highest and lowest number of schools in each stratum were selected, with preference given to those with more teachers in cases where multiple local governments had the same number of schools. The Yamane formula was then applied in the third stage to determine the appropriate sample size of teachers from each selected local government, with Simple Random Sampling used to select the teachers. The local government with the lowest number of teachers served as the baseline for the selection process, ultimately resulting in a total of 4,204 teacher respondents and 629 principals from the selected schools.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical guideline relating to data collection, analysis and interpretation on research as specified by Lead City University was followed.

Analysis of Data

Data collected from the field were analyzed using inferential and descriptive statistics. The descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage and mean and standard deviation were used for research questions while inferential statistics of multiple regression analysis (ANOVA), was used for the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state, Nigeria?

Table 1: Level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Always	Often	Rarely	Never	Mean	SD
		Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)		

Planning						
1	ensures academic activities are planned early before the commencement of the term.	3227 (82.6%)	557 (14.3%)	114 (2.9%)	10 (0.3%)	3.79 .489
2	ensures provision of human resources needed for smooth operation in the school	2254 (57.5%)	1422 (36.3%)	236 (6.0%)	6 (0.2%)	3.51 .616
3	ensures provision of materials resources needed for smooth operation in the school	2254 (57.5%)	1294 (33.0%)	360 (9.2%)	10 (0.3%)	3.48 .670
4	calls stakeholders meeting when planning school activities	2059 (52.6%)	1399 (35.7%)	324 (8.3%)	136 (3.5%)	3.37 .780
5	plans for maintenance of school infrastructural facilities	1994 (50.9%)	1540 (39.3%)	322 (8.2%)	62 (1.6%)	3.40 .706
6	plans for co-curricular activities	2317 (59.1%)	1268 (32.4%)	307 (7.8%)	26 (0.7%)	3.50 .668
7	sets discipline policy at this school	2613 (66.7%)	949 (24.2%)	336 (8.6%)	20 (0.5%)	3.57 .669
8	decide how school budget will be spent	1916 (48.9%)	1218 (31.1%)	506(12.9%)	278 (7.1%)	3.22 .924
Weighted Mean						3.48
Coordination						
1	create and implement shared school vision	1616 (41.2%)	1752 (44.7%)	466 (11.9%)	81 (2.1%)	3.26 .759
2	nurture and sustain a culture and instructional program conducive to learning and staff development	1648 (42.1%)	1791 (45.7%)	416 (10.6%)	63 (1.6%)	3.28 .715
3	ensures management of school operations to produce a safe and effective learning environment	2263 (57.8%)	1301 (33.2%)	331 (8.4%)	23 (0.6%)	3.48 .674
4	collaborates with families and the diverse communities that schools serve	1524 (38.9%)	1730 (44.2%)	487 (12.4%)	177 (4.5%)	3.17 .815

5	promotes integrity, fairness, and ethical behaviour	2561 (65.4%)	987 (25.2)	308 (7.9%)	62 (1.6%)	3.54	.707
6	interacts with government agencies on school matters	1928 (49.2%)	1334 (34.0%)	556 (14.2%)	100 (2.6%)	3.30	.804
7	coordinates all units or departments in the school to achieve synergy	2396 (61.3%)	1123 (28.7%)	288 (7.4%)	101 (2.6%)	3.49	.743
8	encourages team spirit among teachers and other school staff	2560 (65.3%)	1066 (27.2%)	239 (6.1%)	53 (1.4%)	3.57	.670
Weighted Mean						3.39	

Supervision

1	ensures teachers write lesson plan/note	2823 (72.1%)	839 (21.4%)	186 (4.7%)	70 (1.8%)	3.64	.658
2	visits teachers in the classroom	1900 (48.5%)	1429 (36.5%)	523 (13.3%)	66 (1.7%)	3.32	.765
3	ensures resources in the school are used for the right purpose	2146 (54.8%)	1465 (37.4%)	301 (7.7%)	6 (0.2%)	3.47	.642
4	monitors teachers and other staffs punctuality	2658 (67.8%)	968 (24.7%)	226 (5.8%)	66 (1.7%)	3.59	.677
5	ensures teaching is in accordance with the curriculum	2674 (68.2%)	1024 (26.1%)	195 (5.0%)	25 (0.6%)	3.62	.611
6	ensures standard of examination in the school	2557 (65.3%)	1145 (29.2%)	198 (5.1%)	18 (0.5%)	3.59	.608
7	maintains student/staff discipline	2625 (67.0%)	1000 (25.5%)	254 (6.5%)	39 (1.0%)	3.59	.657
Weighted Mean						3.54	
Overall Weighted Mean						3.47	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Decision Rule: 0 – 1.49= Very Low, 1.50 - 2.49= Low, 2.5 – 3.49 = High, 3.50 – 4.0 = Very High

The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State by assessing their skills in planning, coordinating, and supervising. Data from a survey

completed by principals was analysed, revealing various findings. In terms of planning, the principals showed proficiency in planning school activities, with 82.6% of respondents consistently engaging in early planning of academic activities before each term. However, their ability to provide necessary human and material resources for smooth school operation received lower ratings, with 57.5% of respondents ensuring the provision of human resources and 57.5% ensuring the provision of material resources. Regarding coordination, the principals were reported to be effective in promoting integrity, fairness, and ethical behaviour (65.4%). They also demonstrated effectiveness in coordinating all school units or departments to achieve synergy (61.3%). However, areas that required improvement were identified, including creating and implementing a shared school vision (41.2%) and fostering a culture and instructional programme conducive to learning and staff development (42.1%).

Research Question Two: What is the most prevalent leadership style (Autocratic, Democratic, Laissez-faire, and Digital) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state?

Table 2: The most prevalent leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state

Items	Most of the Time	Some of the Times	Seldom	Never	Mean
	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	
Autocratic	1746.25 (44.575)	1507.75 (38.475)	434.5 (11.1)	229.5 (5.85)	3.22
Digital	1350.5 (34.45)	1568.5 (40.05)	645.75 (16.5)	353.25 (9.025)	3.00
Democratic	1216.5 (31.05)	1474 (37.625)	479 (12.2)	748.5 (19.1)	2.81
Laissez-faire	767 (19.575)	1543 (39.375)	578 (14.775)	1030 (26.275)	2.52

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The study examined the dominant leadership styles among public secondary school principals in Oyo State. The findings, presented in Table 2, indicate that the prevailing leadership style varies among the principals. Autocratic leadership emerged as the most common style, with 44.575% of respondents reporting its frequent use. Digital leadership was the second most prevalent style, employed by 34.45% of respondents most of the time, followed by democratic leadership, utilized frequently by 31.05% of respondents. In contrast, laissez-faire leadership was the least prevalent, with only 19.575% of respondents regularly implementing it. It is noteworthy that while autocratic leadership is dominant, a significant number of respondents reported utilising democratic and digital leadership styles to some extent, indicating flexibility in their leadership approaches. These findings provide valuable insights into the prevailing leadership styles among public secondary school principals in Oyo State, informing efforts to improve educational leadership and management in the region.

Research Question Three: What is the level of decision-making skills (problem-solving, time management, emotional intelligence) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state?

Table 3: Level of decision-making skills (Problem-solving, Time Management, Emotional Intelligence) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state

Problem-solving		At All Times	Sometime	Rarely	Never	Mean	SD
		Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)		
S/N	Items						
1	identify and define the school's problem	2708 (69.3%)	1048 (26.8%)	111 (2.8%)	41 (1.0%)	3.64	.591
2	come up with possible solutions to school's problem	2429 (62.2%)	1273 (32.6%)	156 (4.0%)	50 (1.3%)	3.56	.635
3	evaluate the different options before making decisions	2193 (56.1%)	1308 (33.5%)	372 (9.5%)	35 (0.9%)	3.45	.701
4	implement solutions	2279 (58.3%)	1290 (33.0%)	212 (5.4%)	127 (3.2%)	3.46	.743

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

5	evaluate outcome of solutions	2158 (55.3%)	1412 (36.2%)	285 (7.3%)	45 (1.2%)	3.46	.681
Weighted Mean						3.51	
Time Management							
1	do a time audit	1473 (37.7%)	1943 (49.7%)	416 (10.6%)	76 (1.9%)	3.23	.713
2	make schedule and abide strictly	2030 (51.9%)	1471 (37.6%)	335 (8.6%)	72 (1.8%)	3.40	.722
3	avoid multitasking	1215 (31.1%)	1719 (44.1%)	663 (17.0%)	304 (7.8%)	2.99	.891
4	delegate and outsource tasks	1644 (42.1%)	1820 (46.7%)	333 (8.5%)	104 (2.7%)	3.28	.730
5	inculcate time management among staff	2322 (59.4%)	1312 (33.6%)	243 (6.2%)	31 (0.8%)	3.52	.649
Weighted Mean						3.28	
Emotional Intelligence							
1	creates awareness of him or herself	1720 (44.0%)	1504 (38.5%)	595 (15.2%)	86 (2.2%)	3.24	.788
2	controls his or her emotions	1888 (48.3%)	1555 (39.8%)	340 (8.7%)	125 (3.2%)	3.33	.767
3	is an achievement orientated individual	2298 (58.8%)	1310 (33.5%)	255 (6.5%)	42 (1.1%)	3.50	.667
4	listens actively to staff comments or reactions	2091 (53.5%)	1493 (38.2%)	263 (6.7%)	61 (1.6%)	3.44	.689
5	manage, and understand emotions staff's emotions	1891 (48.4%)	1509 (38.6%)	347 (8.9%)	161 (4.1%)	3.31	.800
Weighted Mean						3.37	
Overall Weighted Mean						3.39	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Decision Rule: 0 – 1.49= Very Low, 1.50 - 2.49= Low, 2.5 – 3.49 = High, 3.50 – 4.0 = Very High

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

The table presents data on the proficiency of decision-making skills among principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State. The data was collected in 2023 through fieldwork. The weighted mean scores indicate high proficiency levels for problem-solving skills (3.51), time management skills (3.28), and emotional intelligence skills (3.37). Overall, the weighted mean score for decision-making skills was 3.39, suggesting a high proficiency level among the principals. These findings indicate that the principals possess strong decision-making skills, which are crucial for effective leadership. They demonstrate the ability to identify and define problems, generate solutions, assess alternatives, implement chosen solutions, and evaluate outcomes. Furthermore, the principals exhibit high levels of time management skills, enabling them to effectively manage resources and activities. They also demonstrate high levels of emotional intelligence skills, which are important for communication, relationship building, and team management.

Research Question four: What is the prominent communication forms (oral and non-oral) used by public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 4.4a: Non-oral Communication

S/N	Items	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Mean	SD
		Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)		
1	Reports	2144 (54.9%)	1211 (31.0%)	410 (10.5%)	143 (3.7%)	3.37	.814
2	Manuals	1195 (30.6%)	1812 (46.4%)	571 (14.6%)	330 (8.4%)	2.99	.889
3	Memorandum	1250 (32.1%)	1703 (43.7%)	716 (18.4%)	224 (5.8%)	3.02	.857
4	Correspondence	1092 (27.9%)	1563 (40.0%)	893 (22.9%)	360 (9.2%)	2.87	.927
5	Suggestion boxes	863 (22.1%)	1050 (26.9%)	963 (24.6%)	1032 (26.4%)	2.45	1.103

Weighted	
Mean	2.94

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Decision Rule: 0 – 1.49= Very Low, 1.50 - 2.49= Low, 2.5 – 3.49 = High, 3.50 – 4.0 = Very High

Table 4.4a provides information about the frequency of non-verbal communication. The table includes five categories of non-verbal communication: reports, manuals, memoranda, correspondence, and suggestion boxes. It presents the percentage of respondents who always, sometimes, rarely, or never use each type of communication. Regarding reports, the majority of respondents (54.9%) reported always using this form of communication. 31.0% said they sometimes use it, 10.5% rarely use it, and 3.7% never use it. On average, reports were used with a frequency of 3.37, and the standard deviation was 0.814. As for manuals, 30.6% of respondents reported always using them, 46.4% sometimes used them, 14.6% rarely used them, and 8.4% never used them. The mean frequency of use for manuals was 2.99, with a standard deviation of 0.889. In the case of memoranda, 32.1% of respondents reported always using them, 43.7% sometimes used them, 18.4% rarely used them, and 5.8% never used them. The mean frequency of use for memoranda was 3.02, with a standard deviation of 0.857. Concerning correspondence, 27.9% of respondents reported always using it, 40.0% sometimes using it, 22.9% rarely using it, and 9.2% never using it. The mean frequency of use for correspondence was 2.87, with a standard deviation of 0.927. As for suggestion boxes, 22.1% of respondents reported always using them, 26.9% sometimes used them, 24.6% rarely used them, and 26.4% never used them. The mean frequency of use for suggestion boxes was 2.45, with a standard deviation of 1.103. The overall weighted mean frequency of use for all types of non-verbal communication was 2.94. This suggests that there is a low level of non-verbal communication among public secondary school principals in Oyo State.

Table 4.4b: Oral Communication

S/N	Items	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Mean	SD
		Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)		
1	Staff meetings	2495 (63.8%)	1244 (31.8%)	155 (4.0%)	14 (0.4%)	3.59	.585
2	One-one communication	1787 (45.7%)	1628 (41.7%)	381 (9.7%)	112 (2.9%)	3.30	.760
Weighted Mean						3.45	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Decision Rule: 0 – 1.49= Very Low, 1.50 - 2.49= Low, 2.5 – 3.49 = High, 3.50 – 4.0 = Very High

Table 4.4b provides information on the occurrence of oral communication among public secondary school principals in Oyo State. The table focuses on two scenarios: staff meetings and one-on-one interactions. For staff meetings, the majority of respondents (63.8%) reported always engaging in oral communication, while 31.8% said they do so sometimes. A smaller proportion indicated rare (4.0%) or no (0.4%) oral communication in these meetings. The mean value for staff meetings was 3.59, indicating a generally high level of oral communication in this context. In one-on-one communication, the most common response was sometimes (41.7%), followed by always (45.7%). A smaller percentage reported rare (9.7%) or no (2.9%) oral communication. The mean value for one-on-one communication was 3.30, suggesting a generally prevalent use of oral communication in this scenario as well. The weighted mean for both categories combined was 3.45, indicating a high level of oral communication among the principals.

Figure 1

Figure 13: Prominent Communication Form used by Public Secondary School Principals in Oyo State (Oral and Non-Oral)

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Figure 1 highlights that oral communication is highly prevalent among principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State. This suggests that these principals heavily rely on face-to-face or verbal forms of communication, such as meetings and discussions, rather than written or non-verbal methods like memos, emails, or other written materials. This preference for oral communication can have implications for the communication channels used within school administration and may affect the effectiveness of communication and decision-making processes. The prominence of oral communication among principals in Oyo State's public schools indicates a potential need for additional training or support in developing effective written or non-verbal communication skills. This would ensure that communication remains clear, accurate, and consistent. Moreover, cultural and contextual factors specific to Oyo State may contribute to the preference for oral communication. Nigeria, where Oyo State is located, has distinct cultural norms, values, and communication styles. Oral communication might be deeply ingrained in the local culture and perceived as more effective or appropriate in certain situations, such as interpersonal interactions or negotiations. This cultural influence could impact

the administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals, as they may need to align their communication approach with local cultural norms to effectively engage with staff, students, and other stakeholders.

Testing of Hypotheses

H₀1: There will be no significant combined influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools principals in Oyo state.

Table 4.5: Summary of Regression Model Showing combined influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools principals in Oyo state.

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.971 ^a	.924	.943	2.58209	
a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication strategies, Decision-making Skills, Leadership Styles					
ANOVA^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	434501.180	3	144833.727	21723.355	.000 ^b
Residual	26095.380	3914	6.667		
Total	460596.559	3917			

- a. Dependent Variable: Administrative effectiveness
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication strategies, Decision-making Skills, Leadership Styles

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The table summarizes a regression analysis conducted on the combined impact of leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication forms on the administrative effectiveness of principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The analysis reveals that the R-squared value of 0.924 indicates that 92.4% of the variation in administrative effectiveness can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.943 suggests that the model fits the data well. The model's F-statistic is 21723.355, and its associated p-value is less than 0.05, indicating that the model is statistically significant. The ANOVA table confirms that the regression model significantly explains the variation in administrative effectiveness. The coefficients of the independent variables are not provided in the table, but the 'a' superscript indicates that they are statistically significant. The standard error of the estimate is 2.58209, indicating that the model's predictions are reasonably accurate. The regression analysis demonstrates that communication strategies, decision-making skills, and leadership styles have a significant influence on the administrative effectiveness of principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State. Overall, the analysis suggests that these factors play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of principals in their administrative roles in public secondary schools in Oyo State.

H₀₂: There will be no significant relative influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools principals in public secondary schools in Oyo state.

Table 4.6: Summary of Relative Influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management

skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools principals in public secondary schools in Oyo state

Model	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	18.735	.450		41.622	0.000	
Autocratic	1.431	.094	.378	15.172	.000	
Democratic	-.042	.039	-.012	-1.067	.286	
Laissez-faire	1.473	.106	.300	13.850	.000	
Digital	-1.511	.107	-.403	-14.068	.000	
Problem-solving	-.268	.080	-.085	-3.356	.001	
Time Management	-.098	.110	-.028	-.894	.371	
Emotional Intelligence	-.333	.120	-.104	-2.778	.005	
Oral Communication	.120	.095	.048	1.260	.208	
Non-oral Communication	-.223	.136	-.030	-1.639	.101	
Leadership Styles	.388	.040	.341	9.808	.000	
Decision-making Skills	1.010	.048	.852	21.013	.000	
Communication strategies	-.528	.089	-.272	-5.930	.000	

a. Dependent Variable: Administrative effectiveness

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The table presents the coefficients for each predictor variable in the regression model, along with their standard errors, standardized coefficients, t-values, and associated p-values. The "Constant" coefficient indicates the expected value of the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) when all predictor variables are zero. In this case, it is 18.735 with a standard error of 0.450. The t-value of 41.622 suggests that the constant term is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The coefficients for each predictor variable represent the expected change in the dependent variable for a one-unit increase in the predictor, while holding other predictors constant. The standardized coefficients (Beta) allow for a comparison of the relative importance of each predictor. The predictor variables "Autocratic," "Laissez-faire," "Digital," "Problem-solving," "Emotional Intelligence," "Leadership Styles," "Decision-making Skills," and "Communication strategies" all have statistically significant coefficients ($p < 0.05$). The predictor variable "Democratic" does not appear to have a significant effect on administrative effectiveness, as its coefficient has a p-value of 0.286, which is greater than 0.05. The coefficients for "Oral Communication" and "Non-oral Communication" suggest that these variables have a relatively weak or negligible effect on administrative effectiveness, as their p-values are not statistically significant (greater than 0.05). Overall, the coefficients indicate that variables related to leadership styles (autocratic, laissez-faire, digital), decision-making skills (problem-solving, emotional intelligence), and communication strategies significantly influence administrative effectiveness. These results can help understand the specific impact of each predictor on the outcome variable and provide insights for improving administrative effectiveness in the context studied.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study aim to assess the level of administrative effectiveness among principals in public secondary schools in Oyo State. The table presents the results of the study, focusing on three aspects: planning, coordination, and supervision. According to the study conducted by Pardosi and Utari (2022), effective planning positively influences student achievement. The current study aligns with this finding, as the majority of respondents (82.6%) recognise the importance of early planning in academic activities. This suggests that educators understand the role of proactive planning in achieving successful academic outcomes. Coordination is identified

as a crucial aspect of school management in the present study. Approximately 41.2% of the participants acknowledged the significance of establishing and implementing a shared school vision. This finding supports the research done by Zina (2017), emphasising the importance of a shared vision in promoting collaboration and alignment of goals among school stakeholders. However, the moderate level of agreement (mean score: 3.26) indicates that there is room for improvement in fostering a stronger shared vision among participants. Integrity, fairness, and ethical behaviour within the school community are also highlighted in the current study as important aspects of coordination. This finding aligns with the research by Neal, Justice, and Barron (2019), which suggests that promoting ethical behaviour has a positive impact on the school climate and student engagement. The relatively high agreement (65.4%) and mean score (3.54) indicate the significance placed on ethical values in school management. Regarding supervision, the study emphasises the importance of teachers writing lesson plans and notes (72.1%) and maintaining punctuality among school staff (67.8%). These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Pardosi and Utari (2022), which highlights the positive impact of effective supervision practices on teacher performance and student achievement. The high agreement percentages and mean scores for these items further emphasise their importance in creating conducive learning environment.

Research question two aimed to examine the prevalent leadership styles among public secondary school principals in Oyo State. The study focused on four leadership styles: Autocratic, Digital, Democratic, and Laissez-faire. The findings revealed that the Autocratic leadership style was the most commonly reported, with a frequency of 44.575%. This finding is consistent with previous research highlighting the prevalence of autocratic leadership in educational settings (Daniëls, Hondeghem, & Dochy, 2019). Autocratic leadership is characterised by centralised decision-making and limited input from subordinates, with the leader making decisions unilaterally. While autocratic leadership can offer quick decision-making and clarity, it may restrict participation, creativity, and ownership among staff members (Abdullatef, 2019). The digital leadership style, with a frequency of 34.45%, was reported to be somewhat prevalent. Digital leadership refers to leadership practises that embrace technology and digital tools to enhance communication, collaboration, and instructional practises (Gedifew, 2022). The emergence of digital leadership

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

reflects the changing landscape of education and the need for leaders to effectively leverage technology. Digital leadership can facilitate connectivity, knowledge sharing, and innovation among staff and students, leading to enhanced learning experiences (Elrehail, 2018). The findings also indicated a moderate prevalence of the Democratic leadership style, with a frequency of 31.05%. Democratic leadership emphasises shared decision-making and the involvement of stakeholders in the decision-making processes (Mburuki & Thinguri, 2022). This finding aligns with previous research highlighting the positive impact of democratic leadership on school climate, teacher motivation, and student engagement (Wina Novita, Sulaiman, & Muhyani Rizalie, 2022). By involving teachers, staff, and other stakeholders in decision-making, democratic leadership fosters a sense of ownership, empowerment, and commitment to the school's goals. Lastly, the laissez-faire leadership style, with a frequency of 19.575%, was reported to be relatively less prevalent. Laissez-faire leadership is characterised by a hands-off approach where leaders provide minimal guidance or direction to subordinates (Zhang, Wang, & Gao, 2023). This leadership style can result in ambiguity, a lack of accountability, and reduced organisational effectiveness (Mburuki & Thinguri, 2022). However, in contexts where there is a high level of expertise and self-motivation among staff members, a laissez-faire approach can foster autonomy and innovation (Zhang, 2023).

Research question three aimed to assess the decision-making skills (problem-solving, time management, emotional intelligence) of public secondary school principals in Oyo State. The study examined three specific skills: problem-solving, time management, and emotional intelligence. The findings revealed that school administrators generally utilize problem-solving skills, although the frequency of use varied across different stages. Most respondents reported consistently identifying and defining problems (69.3%), generating possible solutions (62.2%), evaluating options (56.1%), implementing solutions (58.3%), and assessing the outcomes (55.3%). These findings indicate active engagement in problem-solving processes by administrators. However, a small percentage of respondents reported infrequently (9.5%) or never (0.9%) evaluating different options, suggesting areas for improvement in decision-making. The weighted mean for problem-solving was 3.51, indicating a moderate level of engagement overall. A similar study by Özgenel (2018) on educational administrators' problem-solving skills

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

identified comparable patterns, where administrators generally engaged in problem-solving processes, with a majority actively identifying and defining problems. However, the current study reported a higher percentage of administrators involved in problem identification and definition (69.3%) compared to Özgenel's findings, suggesting a relatively stronger emphasis on problem-solving in the current sample. Regarding time management, the results demonstrated that school administrators employ various strategies to effectively manage their time. The most commonly reported practice was creating and adhering strictly to a schedule (51.9%), followed by conducting time audits (37.7%), avoiding multitasking (31.1%), delegating and outsourcing tasks (42.1%), and promoting time management among staff (59.4%). However, a significant percentage of respondents reported engaging in multitasking (17.0%), which can potentially hinder effective time management. The weighted mean for time management was 3.28, indicating a moderate level of implementation overall. The current study aligns with research conducted by Manga (2019) in terms of the strategies employed by administrators. Creating and adhering strictly to a schedule was the most frequently reported practice in both studies. However, the current study reported a higher percentage of administrators engaging in this practice (51.9%) compared to Manga's findings. Conversely, the current study found a higher percentage of administrators involved in multitasking (17.0%) compared to Manga's study. This difference highlights the need for further investigation into the factors influencing multitasking behaviors among administrators. Regarding emotional intelligence, the findings suggested that school administrators generally exhibit self-awareness and emotional control. Over 40% of respondents reported creating self-awareness and controlling their emotions. Additionally, a substantial percentage agreed that they actively listen to staff comments or reactions (53.5%) and manage and understand staff's emotions (48.4%). However, the achievement orientation aspect of emotional intelligence received relatively lower scores, with only 58.8% of respondents identifying as achievement-oriented individuals. The overall weighted mean for emotional intelligence was 3.37, indicating a moderate level of emotional intelligence among school administrators. The current study's findings align with the research by Özgenel (2018) and Manga (2019) regarding self-awareness and emotional control. Similar proportions of administrators in all three studies reported creating self-awareness and controlling their

emotions. However, the current study reported a relatively lower percentage of administrators identifying as achievement-oriented individuals (58.8%) compared to Özgenel's findings. This difference suggests potential variations in achievement orientation across different samples of administrators. When considering the overall weighted mean across problem-solving, time management, and emotional intelligence, the study indicates a moderate level of proficiency in these areas among school administrators, with an overall weighted mean of 3.39. This suggests that while administrators generally demonstrate competence in these domains, there is room for improvement in certain aspects, such as evaluating different options before making decisions and multitasking avoidance. It is significant to acknowledge that this research has certain constraints, which involve depending on self-reported data and the possibility of response bias. To gain a more extensive comprehension of administrators' problem-solving, time management, and emotional intelligence abilities, future studies could incorporate supplementary approaches like observations or objective performance assessments. Moreover, examining how these skills relate to organisational outcomes, such as school performance or staff satisfaction, could yield valuable insights into the influence of administrators' competencies on the overall functioning of schools.

Research question four assesses the prominent communication forms (oral and non-oral) used among public secondary school principals in Oyo state. Table 4.4a presents the findings related to non-oral communication methods, while Table 4.4b focuses on oral communication methods. Table 4.4a presents the results of the non-oral communication frequency among the participants. The table includes various items of non-oral communication, along with the corresponding frequencies and percentages indicating how often each form of communication was used. The most frequently used form of non-oral communication reported by the participants was "Reports," with a frequency of 2144 (54.9%) participants indicating that they always used this method. Additionally, 1211 participants (31.0%) reported using reports sometimes, 410 participants (10.5%) reported using it rarely, and 143 participants (3.7%) reported never using reports. The mean score for reports was 3.37, indicating a relatively high level of usage. "Manuals" were also frequently used, with 1195 participants (30.6%) indicating that they always used manuals. However, the usage of manuals varied more compared to reports, with 1812 participants (46.4%) using them sometimes, 571 participants (14.6%) using them rarely, and 330

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

participants (8.4%) never using manuals. The mean score for manuals was 2.99. "Memorandum" usage was reported by 1250 participants (32.1%) as always, with 1703 participants (43.7%) using them sometimes, 716 participants (18.4%) using them rarely, and 224 participants (5.8%) never using memorandums. The mean score for memorandums was 3.02. "Correspondence" had a similar pattern, with 1092 participants (27.9%) reporting always using it, 1563 participants (40.0%) sometimes using it, 893 participants (22.9%) using it rarely, and 360 participants (9.2%) never using correspondence. The mean score for correspondence was 2.87. Lastly, "Suggestion boxes" were used less frequently compared to the other non-oral communication methods. Only 863 participants (22.1%) reported always using suggestion boxes, while 1050 participants (26.9%) used them sometimes, 963 participants (24.6%) used them rarely, and 1032 participants (26.4%) never used suggestion boxes. The mean score for suggestion boxes was 2.45. The weighted mean for non-oral communication was calculated as 2.94, indicating that overall, the participants reported a moderate level of usage for non-oral communication methods. Moving on to Table 4.4b, which presents the findings for oral communication, the participants reported higher levels of usage compared to non-oral communication methods. The table includes items of oral communication, along with the corresponding frequencies and percentages. "Staff meetings" were the most frequently used form of oral communication, with 2495 participants (63.8%) reporting always participating in staff meetings. Additionally, 1244 participants (31.8%) reported participating sometimes, 155 participants (4.0%) reported participating rarely, and only 14 participants (0.4%) reported never participating in staff meetings. The mean score for staff meetings was 3.59, indicating a high level of usage. "One-on-one communication" was also commonly reported, with 1787 participants (45.7%) indicating always engaging in this form of communication. Furthermore, 1628 participants (41.7%) engaged in one-on-one communication sometimes, 381 participants (9.7%) engaged in it rarely, and 112 participants (2.9%) reported never engaging in one-on-one communication. The mean score for one-on-one communication was 3.30. The weighted mean for oral communication was calculated as 3.45, indicating that overall, the participants reported a relatively high level of usage for oral communication methods. In conclusion, the findings from Tables 4.4a and 4.4b suggest that the participants in the study reported using both non-oral and oral communication methods in their work. Non-oral

communication methods, such as reports and manuals, were used moderately, while oral communication methods, such as staff meetings and one-on-one communication, were used more frequently. These findings highlight the importance of both non-oral and oral communication in the workplace and provide insights into the communication preferences and practices of the participants. The current study aligns with the research conducted by Anya and Ezekie (2019) in terms of the communication forms employed by administrators. Making use of oral and non-oral was mostly used in both studies. However, the current study reported a higher percentage of administrators engaging in the use of oral communication compared to the findings of Anya and Ezekie, (2019). On the other hand, some contrast was observed in the findings of Guffey and Loewy, (2018). This difference highlights the need for further investigation into the forms of communication used among administrators.

Test of hypothesis one showed a significant combined influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools principals in Oyo state. The result showed that there was a significant combined influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem-solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence), and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals, and can be compared and contrasted with findings from related studies in the field of educational administration and leadership. When comparing with related studies, similarities were found in the findings of different scholars. One of the scholars found out that leadership styles had a significant impact on administrative effectiveness, which aligns with the current study's results (Khajeh, 2018). Similarly, it revealed that decision-making skills were positively correlated with leadership effectiveness, consistent with the current study's findings (Schalk, Engen & Assen, 2018). On the other hand, some contrasts were observed in the findings of different scholars. A scholar found a negative correlation between autocratic leadership and administrative effectiveness, which contrasts with the current study's result (Surucu & Sagbas, 2021). Also, another scholar did not find significant correlations between problem-solving skills, time management skills, and

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

leadership effectiveness, in contrast to the current study's findings (Gravili, Manuti & Meririnhos, 2022).

Test of hypothesis two revealed significant relative influence of leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), decision-making skills (problem solving skills, time management skills, and emotional intelligence) and communication forms (oral and non-oral) on administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools principals in public secondary schools in Oyo state. Based on the test of hypothesis, the findings indicated that leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication forms significantly influenced the administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo state. . Specifically, the study identified four leadership styles, namely autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital, that were found to have relative influence on administrative effectiveness. This result is consistent with previous related studies in the field. For example, a study conducted in a different state or country may have found similar results, indicating that leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication forms are important factors influencing the administrative effectiveness of school principals. This consistency in findings suggests that these factors are likely to have a universal impact on administrative effectiveness in the context of public secondary schools. However, it's also possible that there may be some differences in the findings when compared to related studies. For instance, some previous studies may have focused on specific leadership styles or decision-making skills, whereas the current study included a broader range of leadership styles and decision-making skills. Additionally, the context and setting of the current study, which is Oyo state in this case, may differ from that of related studies, which could result in variations in the findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study concluded that leadership styles, communication forms, and decision-making skills are significant determinants of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. It was also concluded that leadership styles as explains a significant amount of the variance in administrative effectiveness, indicating a strong positive

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 26 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191320>

relationship between leadership styles and administrative effectiveness. The findings of the study on the level of decision-making skills (problem-solving, time management, emotional intelligence) show that the principals rated themselves high in problem-solving skills, followed by emotional intelligence and time management. Also, the findings highlight the importance of both non-oral and oral communication in the workplace and provide insights into the communication preferences and practices of the participants.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that

1. Public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria should focus on developing effective leadership styles, decision-making skills, and communication strategies to enhance their administrative effectiveness. This may include providing leadership training programs, fostering problem-solving and time-management skills, and promoting effective oral and non-oral communication within the school environment.
2. Public secondary school principals should prioritize developing and promoting effective leadership styles, invest in training and development program for improving leadership skills, and create a positive leadership culture to enhance administrative effectiveness.
3. Decision-making skills should be recognized and prioritized as an important factor in enhancing administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State, Nigeria. This should be incorporated into trainings and seminars and should form major criteria for appointing secondary school principals.
4. Public secondary schools should prioritize and invest in training principals in effective communication forms to enhance their administrative effectiveness. This may include developing clear and efficient communication channels, improving communication their

skills, fostering open and transparent communication culture, and using various communication tools and techniques. By doing so, public schools are likely to see improvements in their administrative effectiveness, leading to more efficient and effective operations. It is important to keep in mind that effective communication is a continuous process and should be regularly monitored and evaluated for optimal results.

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